

TRADUCEREA LITERATURII DE FICȚIUNE ÎN EPOCA DIGITALĂ: ÎN- TRE TEXT, COD ȘI INTERPRETARE /

TRANSLATING FICTION IN THE DIGITAL AGE: BETWEEN TEXT, CODE AND INTERPRETATION

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This paper explores the role of digital humanities (DH) in reshaping the theory and practice of fiction literature translation in the digital age. It starts from the premise that literary translation is no longer solely a linguistic operation but a complex, digitally mediated act that combines textual interpretation with algorithmic processing. The study examines how DH tools - such as textual corpora, stylometric analysis, visualization platforms (e.g., Voyant Tools), and neural machine translation systems (e.g., DeepL, ChatGPT) - contribute to a better understanding of literary style, narrative coherence, and cultural transfer in translated fiction. By integrating perspectives from translation studies, stylistics, and digital text analysis, the paper argues that the intersection of text, code, and interpretation fundamentally alters both how we translate and how we analyze translations. A practical case study illustrates how digital tools can assist in the comparative analysis of a source text and its translation, focusing on stylistic shifts and interpretive choices. The conclusion highlights that digitalization does not replace the literary translator but redefines their role, expanding their toolkit and encouraging new interdisciplinary approaches to fiction literature translation.